

Research Article

The Detection Of Hepatitis C Virus Infection In Patients Using Hemodialysis In A Laboratory

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ABSTRACT

The invasive procedures and inadequate infection control techniques associated with hemodialysis patients make them more susceptible to contracting the hepatitis C virus (HCV). To stop cross-infection and death/morbidity, early identification and treatment are crucial. But widely used anti-HCV antibody tests aren't accurate enough, thus other tests (such core antigen detection kits) should be looked at as a potential substitute and HCV-combined core antigen-antibody assays performed better than other serological assays in reference to the gold standard HCV RNA. This fourth-generation assay yielded a Kappa value of 0.947 compared with the value of 0.747 and 0.619 for anti-HCV ELISA and rapid detection test and in circumstances with limited resources, fourth-generation HCV ELISA (antigen-antibody combination test) can be used to screen and monitor patients receiving hemodialysis, rather than the routine use of anti-HCV antibody ELISA. A little increase in expenditures will be offset by a higher yield in detection rate.

INTRODUCTION

All around the world, hemodialysis is the accepted treatment method for end-stage renal illness.[1]Patients receiving hemodialysis are more likely than the general population to be infected with the hepatitis C virus (HCV), particularly in low-resource nations.[2-6] There are several possible reasons for this, including increased invasive operations, noncompliance with infection control protocols, and increased prevalence.[7] Effective management and

prevention of HCV epidemics greatly depend on early diagnosis of the virus. Finding anti-HCV antibodies is a frequently employed screening technique.9. But in the first [4-6] weeks following infection (known as the "window period"), these antibodies are not detectable, and in patients receiving hemodialysis, they might not be detected for longer.[10-12] Anti-HCV test positivity is not necessarily indicative of active illness; it can sometimes result from an earlier infection that was treated.[11] In order to classify it as a current

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infection, HCV RNA must be detected using molecular methods (NAT [nucleic acid amplification test])[9] Reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (PCR) may not be practical in settings with low resources due to the costs, knowledge, and infrastructure required. Test tests that look for the HCV core antigen (HCV core Ag) are thought to be a trustworthy screening technique. [3,13] The lengthy window time observed with HCV antibody tests is significantly reduced by using HCV core Ag-based testing, which turn positive just one day following an HCV RNA test. Quantification of HCV core Ag levels may be utilized to monitor patients and anticipate response to treatment, as these levels closely mirror HCV RNA dynamics. [14,15] Because the linearity between core antigen and HCV RNA correlation decreases at a viral load below 3000 IU/ml, HCV core Ag-based assays attain an accuracy to the level of NAT (e.g., HCV RNA PCR) for diagnosing active infection subject to viral load more than 3000 IU/ml [16]. The results of a meta-analysis, however, indicated that chemiluminescence-based techniques (such as Abbott ARCHITECT) are superior to ELISA-based pure core antigen detection techniques. [16] Furthermore, elements including the presence of coinfections (such as the HIV and HBV viruses) and common genotypes may also have an impact on the amount of antigen [16]. In no hemodialysis settings and for laboratory detection of HCV infection, fourth-generation HCV ELISA systems that concurrently detect the core antigen and anti HCV antibody are being employed. These methods can produce very accurate results (specificity as high as 99.8%) when compared to HCV RNA assays [17]. Unfortunately, we were unable to locate any published research on hemodialysis patients from our nation using a fourth-generation HCV ELISA. From some country references research paper published by French study found that combined antigen-

antibody testing kits might detect HCV early in dialysis patients.[18] Another research from Spain indicated that the pure core antigen kit was more sensitive than the combination antigen-antibody detection kit when it came to dialysis patients.[19] In a similar vein, an Egyptian research also discovered that this kit was a suitable substitute for RNA PCR and might be extremely helpful in the early diagnosis of HCV in dialysis patients. There isn't a study that uses the antigen-antibody combination kit from India. A few researches on HCV detection by core antigen have been conducted in India, but none of them made use of the combined antigen-antibody kit. The majority of these investigations came to the conclusion that the HCV core antigen was useful for HIV early diagnosis. [21,22]

Research on cost estimates is challenging as it differs between nations, but on general, HCV core Ag is thought to be far less than HCV RNA. [23–25] Since antigen-based tests are less expensive per test, they may be able to replace nucleic acid testing (NAT) for HCV detection in a more effective manner. This would enable the test to screen for HCV in a larger number of patients. When compared to anti-HCV antibody ELISA, there is a lack of cost-effective analysis for antigen-antibody combination ELISA [1]. The current study was designed to assess the gaps in the fields of HCV diagnosis in dialysis patients due to the lack of data on fourth-generation ELISA from our nation. Specifically, we aimed to assess the diagnostic evaluation of simultaneous HCV antibody antigen detection ELISA against a reference standard HCV RNA testing, as well as the cost-effective analysis of commonly used HCV antibody detection ELISA and simultaneous HCV core Ag-antibody detection assay (fourth-generation ELISA).

METHODS

This was a cross-sectional study in which participants from a tertiary care hospital in South

Bihar, India were hospitalized to a dialysis unit. Blood samples were taken from them. The study included adult subjects (18 years old) who had been on the dialysis unit for at least two months and had tested negative for HIV (anti-HIV antibodies), HBV (hepatitis B virus surface antigen, or HBsAg), and anti-HCV antibodies at either the initial screening or any follow-up screening.[26]. Between October 1, 2015, and January 1, 2017, sample collection and data analysis were conducted as part of a Department of Biotechnology/south Bihar Region Biotechnology Programmed Management Cell funding scheme of the state government. Before they were included in the survey, their prior informed permission was acquired, and the host institute's institutional ethics committee granted ethical clearance. The main test conducted on the subjects was for HCV, and data on age, sex, length of time, and frequency of hemodialysis was gathered from their health records. In accordance, five milliliters (ml) of clotted blood were obtained, serum separated, and aliquoted for testing for HIV, HBsAg, and HCV. Additional biochemical markers, including gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), and so on, were either measured at the host hospital's biochemistry laboratory or obtained from patient records. HCV testing included HCV core Ag with fourth-

generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA of Bio-Rad's Monolisa make (HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay); HCV RNA testing by real-time PCR (HCV kit and manual pure nucleic acid extraction kit in Roche Cobas TaqMan 48 cycler); and anti-HCV antibody detection by immunochromatography (ICT)-based rapid detection test (RDT) of Tulip make. Throughout the testing, the kit insert for these chemicals was adhered to scrupulously. The statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) was utilized to analyses the data. Whereas continuous variables were reported in terms of mean, standard deviation, range, median, upper quartile (UQ), and lower quartile (LQ), if appropriate, categorical variables were expressed as percentages (%). With conventional metrics including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy with 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs), all screening assays were tested against the gold standard HCV RNA assay. Kappa statistic (k) with 95% CI values was used to assess agreement between the HCV RNA test and other screening tests, such as RDT, third-generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA, and HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay. Anti-HCV third-generation ELISA and fourth-generation (antigen-antibody combination) ELISA was the subject of a cost-effective investigation, and the findings were reported in tabular form.

Table1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Populations

Sr. No.	Demographic and treatment characteristics	Study participants (N = 270)
01	Male: female ratio (%)	
02	Age (in years) Median (LQ, UQ) Mean (SD) Range	52 (45, 66) 51 (15.3) 24–81
03	Duration of hemodialysis (in months) Median (LQ-UQ) Mean (SD)	15 (5–21) 15 (6)

	Range	2–27
04	Frequency of hemodialysis Median (LQ-UQ) Mean (SD) Range	82 (46–137) 89 (47) 4–234
05	Diagnosis Diabetics Non-diabetics	109 (40.37) 161 (59.63)
06	Dialyzer Re-use Non-reuse	157 (58.15) 113 (41.85)
07	Dialysis at One center (current one) Two centers Three or more center	163 (60.4) 102 (37.8) 5 (1.8)

RESULT

Table 1 displays the initial characteristics of each of the 270 patients that were recruited. Regardless of the presence of HCV infection, levels of AST, ALT, and GGT were less than 40IU/L, 31.9% (86/270) of the samples had HCV RNA detected; the HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA test yielded positive results in 83 out of 86 samples. In the HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay, none of the HCV RNA-negative patients had positive results (Table 2). Three HCV RNA positive patients had low viral loads, or less than 1000 IU/ul, whereas fourth generation ELISA (i.e., Ag-Ab ULTRA test) negative cases did. 11.4% (23/202) of the third-generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA negative rate (202/270) had positive HCV RNA. Of the 68 seropositive

individuals, about 11.5% had HCV RNA negative results. Table 2 unequivocally demonstrates that the HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA test has more sensitivity and specificity than the third-generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA. Table 2 shows that the HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay has comparable PPV, NPV, and accuracy to the third-generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA test. Compared to HCV RNA and third-generation anti-HCV antibody ELISA ($k = 0.947$), the agreement between HCV RNA and HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay assays was much superior. When compared to the reference standard HCV RNA test, similar characteristics of the anti-HCV quick test (ICT-based) performed worse than those of the other two tests.

Laboratory testing for HCV in South Bihar Indian dialysis cases

DISCUSSION

Globally, HCV infection is a hazard that is regularly experienced by the population receiving chronic hemodialysis.[4,8] It significantly raises this group of people's chance of dying.[27, 28] To reduce the negative effects of infection, early identification and timely antiviral therapy are essential.[29] In addition, timely identification has a significant role in halting the transmission of infection, which would otherwise be effective in susceptible patients receiving hemodialysis that involves several invasive procedures.[7,30] When it comes to diagnosing HCV infection in this patient population in its early stages, biochemical indicators are not very helpful. A total of 270 hemodialysis patients, including those with active HCV infection (HCV RNA-positive), had aminotransferase levels less than 40 IU/L in the current research. This showed strong correlations with previous research.[7,30] In 7.3% of antibody-positive individuals, there was no detectable HCV, whereas 11.4% of seronegative cases had HCV RNA. These results were consistent with those of earlier research studies.[10] Our research confirms prior findings that fourth-generation HCV (core Antibody combination detection) assay-based investigations are superior than third-generation anti-HCV antibody detection. In addition to having significantly higher sensitivity and specificity, a 100% specificity in comparison to the gold standard HCV RNA testing is remarkable. However, a 98.4% NPV indicates that 1.6% of anti-HCV antibody negative individuals also had positive HCV RNA results. Unlike our antigen-antibody combination test, several Indian research on core antigen-based HCV detection in dialysis patients mostly employed pure core antigen detection kits. The antigen detection kit was found to be unhelpful in one previous study from South Bihar [32] because of the poor results; but, in another earlier investigation, the same authors determined that the test was beneficial,

particularly during pre-seroconversion.[22] This can be the result of earlier tests' inability to identify combination antigen. Core antigen tests that are now available may identify both free and mixed antigen. A study conducted in Delhi suggested that HCV core antigen ELISA should be used in dialysis patients since it can shorten the window time, which is often longer in these situations.[21] Thirteen of the fourteen preseroconversion window period patients were found to be core antigen-positive cases in a research conducted in Delhi by Chakravarti et al. [33]. They suggested it as an alternative to HCV PCR in locations with limited resources. The total HCV in patients receiving hemodialysis was determined by Jindal et al.34 to be 32%; this figure is quite comparable to what we discovered. Compared to our finding of 1.6% of cases (we utilized an antigen-antibody combination test), they found HCV RNA in 2.8% of core antigen-negative patients. However, in dialysis instances, Mahajan et al.35 suggested both antibody-based and HCV RNA-based testing. It is uncommon to find combined HCV antigen-antibody kit-based research in dialysis patients from India. Few studies from outside were uncovered by us, and one such French study revealed that combination kits identify HCV infection 21.6 days earlier than antibody detection tests.18 An Egyptian investigation also came to a similar result.20 Antigen-antibody combination detection (ELISA) proved to be more sensitive than only core antigen detection in patients receiving hemodialysis, according to research comparing Ag-Ab combined kit with pure antigen detection kit. Three patients in the current investigation had viral loads less than 650 IU/ml, making them undetectable using the fourth-generation (antigen-antibody ELISA kit) assay. We had a 1.6% false negative rate (3/187). Chakravarti et al. [33] from India observed that the threshold viral load for pure core antigen-based tests producing false negative findings was higher

at 4500 IU/ml. A few further studies also showed comparable results for tests based only on core antigens [3]. Attention must be paid to the implications of low HCV virus load in dialysis patients. Although HCV-induced occult hepatitis infection (OCI) has been described, it is said to have no practical consequences or significance. OCI is defined as the identification of HCV RNA in kidney or peripheral mononuclear cells in serum HCV RNA negative subjects.³⁸ Similar to the previous example, an infection with a very low viral load (detectable by fourth-generation ELISA) may also have less clinical consequences, although there is a considerable danger of transmission (between dialysis units). To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first in our nation to use Ag-Ab combined Ultra ELISA, a fourth generation of ELISA, on hemodialysis patients. Given its advantages in sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and other areas, it is obvious that the fourth-generation kit may be a superior substitute. Aside from cost, another benefit over pure core antigen-based kits may be a decreased risk of false negative (lower threshold viral load) (Supplementary data table). The fourth-generation kit offers the benefits of pure core antigen-based assays, such as effective correlation with HCV viremia (HCV RNA findings), as core antigen is an integral target. Fourth-generation kits are more costly than third-generation (antibody-based) kits; however, in terms of yield, the former is ultimately more desirable and practical, particularly considering

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that no new infrastructure is required for development (apart from the ELISA facility that is already closed). Another thing to consider would be if fourth-generation kits are still available in India; at the moment, just one company sells them there. However, if it is widely accepted, additional producers would undoubtedly adopt it and bring it to market. The National Viral Hepatitis Control Programmed, a major initiative of the Indian government, aims to establish robust laboratory infrastructure, including ELISA facilities, PCR setups, and other procedures, starting at the district level of laboratories. While only antibody detection (ELISA and rapid test) and PCR are advised for HCV establishment of ELISA, antigen detection (or antigen–antibody detection) is not included. However, given its advantage over antibody-based ELISA, antigen-based ELISA will undoubtedly be facilitated in the future by district-level facilities. Effective HCV transmission in susceptible populations, such as dialysis patients, makes early infection identification crucial, primarily to avoid cross-infection in dialysis facilities and to start treatment at the acute stage. Finally, we suggest that fourth-generation HCV (e.g., HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA assay) ELISA be used for regular screening of patients receiving hemodialysis in place of the commonly used anti-HCV antibody-based assays. Even lower resource settings can benefit from the HCV Ag-Ab ULTRA test due to its cost-effectiveness and decreased labor-intensiveness.

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